

JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES

Scientific and Academy Journal

Print ISSN 2222-7288

Online ISSN 2518-5551

IMPACT FACTOR VALUE OF 2.329

Vol. (46/2)–SPECIAL ISSUE JULY-2025

**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
GOVERNANCE IN THE UKRAINIAN EXPERIENCE**

**8. Legal Framework for the Professional
Selection of Forensic Experts to Ensure Impartial
Judgements. By ROMAN KIRIN. and others.**

p. 161.

CENTER FOR LAW AND POLITICAL RESEARCH-DENMARK

AALBORG ACADEMY OF SCIENCES – DENMARK

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JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES (JLPS)

P.ISSN 2222-7288 E. ISSN 2518-5551

VOL. 45-2-ISSUE 3-June 2025 -Special issue

JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES

SCIENTIFIC AND ACADEMY JOURNAL

Print ISSN 2222-7288

Online ISSN 2518-5551

IMPACT FACTOR VALUE OF 2.701

VOL. (46/2) SPECIAL ISSUE JULY 2025

FIRST EDITION 2011

SPECIAL ISSUE

**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
GOVERNANCE IN THE UKRAINIAN EXPERIENCE**

A GROUP OF UNIVERSITY GRADUATES IN UKRAINE

PREPARED

**CENTER FOR LAW AND POLITICAL RESEARCH – DENMARK
FACULTY OF LAW - ACADEMY OF THE AALBORG – DENMARK**

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JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES (JLPS)

P.ISSN 2222-7288 E. ISSN 2518-5551

First edition 2011

IMPACT FACTOR 2.329

VOL. 45-2-ISSUE 3-June 2025 -Special issue

The Journal certified by:

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JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES (JLPS)

P.ISSN 2222-7288 E. ISSN 2518-5551

IMPACT FACTOR 2.329

VOL. 45-2-ISSUE 3-June 2025 -Special issue

First edition 2011

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**LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE PROFESSIONAL
SELECTION OF FORENSIC EXPERTS TO ENSURE
IMPARTIAL JUDGEMENTS**

Receipt 21May

Approval 30 June

Publishing July 2025

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ABSTRACT

The analysis of the norms and requirements of current legislation in the regulation of attestation, qualification and the actual activities of forensic experts reveals the existence of gaps and the unregulated nature of this area. This leads to an increase in the duration, a decrease in the quality of expertise, and an excessive workload. This issue is critical against the background of a significant number of wartime crimes committed by the Russian Federation on the territory of Ukraine after the full-scale invasion. The article aims to analyse the legal aspects of the professional selection of forensic experts to ensure objective conclusions. The study is

descriptive and based on case studies and secondary data analysis. The study identifies the main prerequisites for the current situation in forensic examination, including the lack of unified requirements for the competences of forensic experts, the unregulated procedure for their certification, the inaccessibility of internships and advanced training, and others. In Ukraine, forensic expert activity is carried out by specialists of state institutions and private experts. The author identifies the determinants of forensic experts' professional qualifications and the relevant limitations. The rights and obligations of forensic experts as defined by current legislation are analysed. The professional competences of a modern forensic expert in different countries and the increased risk of war crimes are characterised. The specifics of the activities of the Central Expert Qualification Commission, information on certified forensic experts in the regional context and areas of expertise in the Register of Forensic Experts are studied. The paper proposes optimising amendments to existing legislative acts aimed at improving the training process and maintaining the level of qualification and professional selection of forensic experts.

Keywords: *forensic expert, forensic examination, professional competence, professional selection, certification, Register of Certified Forensic Experts.*

INTRODUCTION

The practical implementation of legislative norms and requirements and the delivery of reasoned court decisions are impossible without the established and developed expert support of the justice process. A modern forensic examination should not only be categorically independent and highly qualified but also complement the requirements of international law and involve innovative scientific and technical solutions.

Given the above, the role of a forensic expert as a competent and influential specialist who demonstrates outstanding awareness and professional objectivity and possesses unique knowledge and practical skills necessary for conducting relevant expert research is constantly growing. The role of a forensic expert is vital in investigating war crimes, which makes it a priority to upgrade the system of training and internships for forensic experts and improve approaches to the professional selection of highly qualified specialists in the field.

New requirements and approaches to solving crimes, including war crimes, require a systematic update of the specialised knowledge base and mastery of modern research methodology by existing forensic experts. In the field of professional training of experts, special attention should be paid to the process of professional selection of forensic experts, which is regulated by regulatory requirements. Against the backdrop of

Ukraine's active European integration and the growing risks of war crimes, this issue is of particular relevance.

The specifics of the legal selection of forensic experts ensure that several modern scholars study the justice process and are of current research interest in the scientific field. In particular, proposals to improve the system of training and certification of forensic experts have been made by such scholars as Perederii¹, Levkivskiy², Savrasov et al.³, Bazhaniuk⁴. The variability of qualification requirements for forensic experts in different countries was studied by Neal et al.⁵, Bali et al.⁶, and Coulthard⁷. The issues of guaranteeing the objectivity of forensic examination conclusions are within the scope of the research interests of Dror and Pierce⁸, van Straalen et al.⁹, Rodríguez Almada et al.¹⁰. Several authors^{11, 12, 13} have proposed ways to improve the reliability of expert opinions, as well as a system for ensuring the appropriate level of expert qualification.

¹Perederii, O. (2022). Problems of reforming the domestic judicial system in the context of intensification of Ukraine's European integration (theoretical and legal aspect). *Scientific Bulletin of Uzhhorod National University. Series: Law*, 1(72), 61-66. <https://doi.org/10.24144/2307-3322.2022.72.10>

² Levkivskiy, Yu. (2024). Features of the participation of a legal expert in a trial. *Topical issues in modern science*, 6(24). [https://doi.org/10.52058/2786-6300-2024-6\(24\)](https://doi.org/10.52058/2786-6300-2024-6(24))

³ Savrasov, M., Okorokov, R., & Mikheieva, M. (2023). Metacognitive factors of professional success of the subject of forensic activity. *Bulletin of the HNPU named after GS Skovoroda "Psychology"*, 68, 293-305. <http://journals.hnpu.edu.ua/index.php/psychology/article/view/13439>

⁴ Bazhaniuk, V. V. (2023). *Legal and organisational and tactical bases of conducting examinations in criminal proceedings*. Kropyvnytskyi: Donetsk State University of Internal Affairs. https://dnuvs.ukr.education/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/bazhanyuk_dysertacziya.orig_.pdf

⁵ Neal, T. M., Martire, K. A., Johan, J. L., Mathers, E. M., & Otto, R. K. (2022). The law meets psychological expertise: Eight best practices to improve forensic psychological assessment. *Annual Review of Law and Social Science*, 18(1), 169-192. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-lawsocsci-050420-010148>

⁶ Bali, A. S., Edmond, G., Ballantyne, K. N., Kemp, R. I., & Martire, K. A. (2020). Communicating forensic science opinion: An examination of expert reporting practices. *Science & Justice*, 60(3), 216-224. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scijus.2019.12.005>

⁷ Coulthard, M. (2020). Experts and opinions: In my opinion. In: M. Coulthard, A. May, & R. Sousa-Silva (eds.), *The Routledge handbook of forensic linguistics* (pp. 523-538). Routledge. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9780429030581-41/experts-opinions-malcolm-coulthard>

⁸ Dror, I. E., & Pierce, M. L. (2020). ISO standards addressing issues of bias and impartiality in forensic work. *Journal of Forensic Sciences*, 65(3), 800-808. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1556-4029.14265>

⁹ van Straalen, E. K., de Poot, C. J., Malsch, M., & Elffers, H. (2020). The interpretation of forensic conclusions by criminal justice professionals: The same evidence interpreted differently. *Forensic Science International*, 313, 110331. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forsciint.2020.110331>

¹⁰ Rodríguez Almada, H., Passalacqua, N. V., Congram, D., & Pilloud, M. (2021). As forensic scientists and as people, we must not confuse objectivity with neutrality. *Journal of Forensic Sciences*, 66(5). <https://doi.org/10.1111/1556-4029.14785>

At the same time, despite the significant contribution of modern scholars to the field of research on improving forensic examination processes, aspects of the professional selection of forensic experts require additional research, especially in the context of legal support dictated by the dynamics of the conditions for the implementation of forensic examination in wartime and in the context of active European integration development.

The article aims to analyse the legal aspects of the professional selection of forensic experts to ensure objective conclusions.

Literature review

The limits of the influence of the human factor as a potential risk of error in the process of forensic examination are actively studied by many scientists. In particular, the authors Abbasov¹⁴, Christensen et al.¹⁵, and Baechler et al.¹⁶ analyse the most common errors of forensic experts. First, the researchers differentiate them by possible sources of origin and distinguish method errors, instrumentation errors, statistical errors, and errors as a manifestation of the human factor. Furthermore, Dror and Pierce¹⁷, Spellman et al.¹⁸ consider expert errors in the context of randomness or systematicity and divide them into those caused by negligence and those caused by incompetence.

¹¹ Jühling, M., König, L. M., Gruber, H., Wolf, V., Ritz-Timme, S., & Mayer, F. (2023). Impact of (forensic) expert opinions according to the Istanbul Protocol in Germany-results and insights of the in: Fo-project. *International Journal of Legal Medicine*, 137(3), 863-873. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00414-023-02950-1>

¹² Airlie, M., Robertson, J., Krosch, M. N., & Brooks, E. (2021). Contemporary issues in forensic science-Worldwide survey results. *Forensic Science International*, 320, 110704. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forsciint.2021.110704>

¹³ Crispino, F., Weyermann, C., Delémont, O., Roux, C., & Ribaux, O. (2022). Towards another paradigm for forensic science? *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Forensic Science*, 4(3), e1441. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wfs2.1441>

¹⁴ Abbasov, N. (2022). Criteria for assessing the quality of forensic activities in different countries of the world. *Law. Human. Environment*, 13(3), 7-16. <https://doi.org/10.31548/law2022.03.001>

¹⁵ Christensen, A.M., Crowder, C.M., Houck, M.M., & Ousley, S.D. (2011). Error, error rates and their meanings in forensic science. *Proceedings of the 63rd Annual Meeting of the American Academy of Forensic Sciences* (Feb 21-26; Chicago, IL). Colorado Springs, CO: American Academy of Forensic Sciences. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1556-4029.12275>

¹⁶ Baechler, S., Morelato, M., Gittelson, S., Walsh, S., Margot, P., Roux, C., & Ribaux, O. (2020). Breaking the barriers between intelligence, investigation and evaluation: A continuous approach to define the contribution and scope of forensic science. *Forensic Science International*, 309, 110213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forsciint.2020.110213>

¹⁷ Dror, I. E., & Pierce, M. L. (2020). *Id.*

¹⁸ Spellman, B. A., Eldridge, H., & Bieber, P. (2022). Challenges to reasoning in forensic science decisions. *Forensic Science International: Synergy*, 4, 100200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fsisyn.2021.100200>

As noted by Biedermann and Kotsoglou¹⁹, expert error often occurs today as a result of digital incompetence or the inability of a specialist to select and apply modern research methodology properly. At the same time, the weight and frequency of errors can be significantly reduced by using modern quality control systems, constantly improving the qualifications of forensic experts, and applying the latest research methods.

The specifics of a particular type of forensic examination largely determine the specifics of a particular type of forensic examination. In this context, Arkes and Koehlandr²⁰ propose ways to minimise the risk of expert errors and guarantee the reliability of expert results. At the same time, the researchers position the effective professional selection of forensic experts as crucial.

The scientific basis for research on the modern issues of legal support for forensic examination is formed by Doyle²¹, De Kinder and Pirée²² and others. In particular, Doyle²³ conducts a comparative analysis of the regulatory and legal support for the activities of forensic experts in the spatial and temporal context. The author describes the changes in the latest editions' structure, content and scope and assesses the impact on forensic science. In contrast, De Kinder and Pirée²⁴ propose various ways of exchanging expert experience internationally. The researchers conducted a comparative analysis of the norms of expert activity worldwide and formed a model for effectively implementing a sectoral forensic structure.

Horsman and Shavers's²⁵ publications analyse aspects of forensic expert training and advanced training. The authors emphasise that the current conditions for forensic expert certification require an upgrade of the methodology for their training in accordance with international law.

¹⁹ Biedermann, A., & Kotsoglou, K. N. (2021). Forensic science and the principle of excluded middle: "Inconclusive" decisions and the structure of error rate studies. *Forensic Science International: Synergy*, 3, 100147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fsisyn.2021.100147>

²⁰ Arkes, H. R., & Koehler, J. J. (2021). Inconclusions and error rates in forensic science: a signal detection theory approach. *Law, probability and risk*, 20(3), 153-168. <https://doi.org/10.1093/lpr/mgac005>

²¹ Doyle, S. (2020). A review of the current quality standards framework supporting forensic science: Risks and opportunities. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Forensic Science*, 2(3), e1365. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wfs2.1365>

²² De Kinder, J., & Pirée, H. (2020). The future of the forensic science providers-Time to re-think our structures? *Forensic Science International*, 316, 110471. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forsciint.2020.110471>

²³ Doyle, S. (2020). *Id.*

²⁴ De Kinder, J., & Pirée, H. (2020). *Id.*

²⁵ Horsman, G., & Shavers, B. (2022). Who is the digital forensic expert and what is their expertise? *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Forensic Science*, 4(5), e1453. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wfs2.1453>

The professional suitability of a particular person for effective practice in the field of forensic examination is considered by researchers in different contexts: from the standpoint of structural and functional features of professional training of experts, in the context of psychological qualities of a person or ethics of expert activity, from the standpoint of a competence-based approach. In particular, Neuteboom et al.²⁶ are convinced that the expert's personality is manifested in the effectiveness of his or her practical professional activity, which, in turn, depends on the expert's qualification level, competence, as well as his or her personal qualities and management skills

Levin et al.²⁷ further assert that a forensic expert's procedural status implies that he or she is personally responsible for the conclusions formed based on the principle of internal conviction. According to the scholars, this principle is the basis for the objectivity of the forensic expert's opinion, which should be regulated by the relevant regulatory requirements.

In general, the issues of legal regulation of the process of professional selection of forensic experts remain poorly understood, given the dynamic nature of the problem. These issues are of particular importance in times of war, as the primary focus is ensuring objectivity in the forensic examination of war crimes.

Materials and methods

The study uses a combined approach to examine the impact of legal aspects of the professional selection of forensic experts in different contexts. This study is descriptive and includes case studies and analysis of secondary data. The research procedure consisted of two main stages: data collection and analysis. Primary data sources were used in the first stage, which was obtained by analysing industry statistics and publications. Publications indexed in the leading scientific databases Scopus and Web of Science were used. The keywords used for the search were "forensic expert, forensic examination, professional competences, professional selection, certification, Register of Certified Forensic Experts".

The criteria for including and excluding publications were the spatial and temporal indicator and the information's reliability level. Methods used to assess the risk of bias in the included studies included brainstorming and causal analysis. Initially, more than fifty industry publications were collected, and twenty-five of them were used for the study according to the defined criteria.

²⁶ Neuteboom, W., Ross, A., Bugeja, L., Willis, S., Roux, C., & Lothridge, K. (2024). Quality Management in forensic science: A closer inspection. *Forensic Science International*, 358, 111779. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forsciint.2023.111779>

²⁷ Levin, A. P., Putney, H., Crimmins, D., & McGrath, J. G. (2021). Secondary traumatic stress, burnout, compassionate satisfaction, and perceived organisational trauma readiness in forensic science professionals. *Journal of Forensic Sciences*, 66(5), 1758-1769. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1556-4029.14747>

This sample size was deemed appropriate in view of practical realities while ensuring sufficient statistical power. The study focuses on informative data from recent years and indicators from different countries regarding the professional selection of forensic experts.

The study used several general scientific methods, including analysis and synthesis (to study modern theoretical concepts and scientific developments in this area and clarify terminology), comparison (to systematise conceptual approaches to defining basic concepts and criteria and identify related risks and obstacles), and a structural and logical method (to develop proposals for improving the organisational mechanism). These methods were adapted to the focus of the study in the legal sphere and the unique characteristics of wartime.

The study's main conclusions were formed by deduction. In this case, abstraction was used as a process of mental detachment from the standard properties of concepts while simultaneously focusing on the essential properties sought. Comparison made it possible to identify the qualitative and quantitative characteristics of the organisational practices of legal regulation of the issues under study, their similarities and differences.

Quantitative research focuses on numerical data that can be evaluated using statistical tools. Microsoft Excel tools are used to perform the analysis. Qualitative research focuses on rich, detailed data that can provide insight into the experience and current perspectives on improving the legal framework for the professional selection of forensic experts to promote the principles of the objectivity of justice.

2: LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK FOR THE PROFESSIONAL SELECTION OF FORENSIC EXPERTS

The priority role in conducting forensic examinations is given to expert specialists whose experience and qualifications can determine the objectivity and correctness of a court decision. In Ukraine, private experts and specialists of specialised state institutions carry out forensic expert activities. For example, the Law of Ukraine "On Forensic Expertise"²⁸ stipulates that these may be "state specialised institutions, their territorial branches, expert institutions of municipal ownership, as well as forensic experts who are not employees of the said institutions, and other specialists (experts) in the relevant fields of knowledge".

By the Law of Ukraine "On Forensic Expertise"²⁹, the state specialised institutions include research institutions of forensic examinations, forensic medical and forensic psychiatric institutions of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine; research institutions of forensic examinations of the Ministry of Justice of Ukraine; expert services of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine, the Ministry of Defence of

²⁸On Forensic Expertise. Law of Ukraine of 25.02.1994 No. 4038-XII. (1994). *Verhovna Rada of Ukraine*. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/4038-12>

²⁹Verhovna Rada of Ukraine. (1994). *Id.*

Ukraine, the Security Service of Ukraine and the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine. In addition, the aforementioned Law stipulates that the following specialists may act as forensic experts:

- have a relevant higher education and have an educational qualification level not lower than a specialist;
- have undergone appropriate professional training;
- qualified as a forensic expert.

The legal framework regulates restrictions on the position of a forensic expert. Thus, a person who has been declared incapacitated by the procedure established by law or who has an unexpunged or unspent criminal record cannot be a forensic expert. In addition, the above professional functions cannot be performed by a person subject to an administrative penalty for committing an offence in the field of corruption risks during the current year.

2-1: RIGHTS AND RESPONSIBILITIES OF A FORENSIC EXPERT IN UKRAINE

Current legislation defines a forensic expert's rights and ensures the proper and objective performance of their procedural duties (Table 1).

Table 1. Fundamental rights and obligations of a forensic expert in Ukraine

The rights of a forensic expert	Duties of a forensic expert
With the permission of the person or body who appointed the forensic examination, to be present during investigative or judicial actions and to file motions related to the subject of forensic examination.	Provide the necessary explanations regarding the conclusion given by him/her at the request of the judge, court, person or body that engaged the expert.
To indicate in the expert's opinion the facts directly identified in the course of the forensic examination, which is characterised as relevant to the case and about which he was not asked questions.	Recuse themselves in cases stipulated by law and in the presence of grounds that exclude the participation of an expert in a particular case.
Submit a request for additional materials related to the subject matter of the forensic examination.	Conduct a full investigation and provide an objective and reasoned written opinion.
Receive remuneration for conducting a forensic examination if its performance is not an official task.	
To conduct expert research on issues of interest to legal entities and individuals on a contractual basis, subject to the restrictions provided for by law.	

To file complaints against the actions of the person in charge of the case if these actions violate the rights of the forensic expert.

Source: compiled by the author based on the Law of Ukraine “On Forensic Expertise”³⁰

An expanded version of the duties and rights of forensic experts is provided in the Instruction on the appointment and conduct of forensic examinations and expert studies³¹, approved by the Order of the Ministry of Justice of Ukraine No. 53/5 dated 08.10.1998. According to this Instruction, the following duties are imposed on the expert, which, together with the above, serve as the basis for professional selection:

- accept the assigned expertise for practical implementation;
- personally carry out the necessary complete research by the procedure established by law;
- to formulate and present in writing the most reliable and objective opinion and, if necessary, provide additional explanations;
- if necessary, to notify in writing the body that appointed the expert if the task exceeds the expert’s competence and if there are several other restrictions and conditions;
- if summoned by the body that appointed the expert examination, to appear to provide additional explanations regarding the expert examination;
- to ensure maximum preservation of the material object of examination
- to ensure the confidentiality of information that becomes known to the expert in the course of the expert’s direct performance of professional duties.

3: DETERMINANT PERSONAL AND PROFESSIONAL QUALITIES OF A FORENSIC EXPERT

The psychological qualities necessary for forensic experts and as an important factor in professional selection are formed, for the most part, directly in the process of practical professional activity. Among the qualities that determine an expert’s professional unfitness are mental disability and defects of the senses. At the same time, the main psychophysiological qualities of a forensic expert are psychological endurance and emotional balance, as well as the ability to concentrate for a long time and quickly switch to diverse tasks.

Scientific methods are proposed for recruitment. For example, psychological testing, observation, experimental testing of psychophysical qualities, and the method of generalisation of independent characteristics allow the identification of the

³⁰ Verhovna Rada of Ukraine. (1994). *Id.*

³¹ Instruction on the appointment and conduct of forensic examinations and expert studies: Order of the Ministry of Justice of Ukraine of 08.10.1998 No. 53/5. (1998). *Verhovna Rada of Ukraine*. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/z0705-98#Text>

psychophysiological characteristics of a specialist necessary for the adequate performance of his or her professional duties as a forensic expert.

The law regulates the list of grounds for challenging a forensic expert, in particular:

- if a forensic expert has a personal direct or indirect interest in a particular expert opinion;
- if the expert is related to the parties to the conflict under consideration;
- if it is established that the forensic expert has unique relations with persons involved in the case under examination;
- in the case of a previous audit conducted by the expert, the materials of which served as a direct basis for initiating the case in which the expert examination is being conducted;
- if the forensic expert is in an established dependence on persons or parties involved in the case;
- in the event of an expert's incompetence being established.

Thus, a forensic expert today must be a competent, educated specialist. In addition, an expert in practice must assimilate fundamental professional training and innovative competences, be characterised by a high level of civic consciousness, and continuously improve his or her professional knowledge and skills.

It is worth noting that currently, in Ukraine, the existing system of regulatory and legal support for forensic examination does not provide for differentiation by type of examination and is universal. The current state of affairs does not meet the requirements of the modern international legal framework in the justice field, and wartime risks dictate the new conditions. In this regard, the need to specify the requirements for the professional competences of a forensic expert is becoming more urgent. Currently, these requirements are within the competence of expert qualification commissions, which assign and deprive a forensic expert of qualifications. Such commissions are composed of the most experienced specialists and scientists with the qualifications of forensic experts and at least five years of practical experience in the speciality.

State forensic experts hold positions of various categories with specific qualification requirements per the Handbook of Qualification Characteristics of Positions of Employees of Forensic Research Institutions of the Ministry of Justice³². Information on certified forensic experts is reflected in the Register³³, which is regulated by the Procedure for Maintaining the State Register of Certified Forensic Experts³⁴, approved by Order of the Ministry of Justice of Ukraine No. 492/5 dated 29.03.2012.

³² Handbook of Qualification Characteristics of Positions of Employees of Forensic Research Institutions of the Ministry of Justice of Ukraine: Order of the Ministry of Justice of Ukraine of 19.04.2012 No. 611/5. (2012). *Verhovna Rada of Ukraine*. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/v0611323-12#Text>

³³ Register of certified forensic experts. (n.d.) <https://data.gov.ua/dataset/0a556891-d6ef-4a5f-a182-caac2f7aa9c9/resource/c89d0270-c87a-4781-a96b-41def560c6fc?page=11>

³⁴ Procedure for maintaining the State Register of Certified Forensic Experts: Order of the Ministry of Justice of Ukraine of 29.03.2012 No. 492/5. (2012). *Verhovna Rada of Ukraine*. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/z0484-12#Text>

4: WAYS TO OPTIMIZE THE PROFESSIONAL SELECTION OF FORENSIC EXPERTS

The analysis of the legal regulation of the certification and training of forensic experts, the assignment of qualifications to them, and their practical activities convincingly demonstrates several gaps and apparent unresolved issues^{35, 36}. In order to mitigate the shortcomings, it is considered necessary to introduce several measures, in particular

- to carry out the procedure of unification of the procedural legislation of Ukraine on forensic examination;
- to provide favourable conditions for the development of higher professional education in the field of forensic science;
- to reduce the cost of advanced training and internships for forensic experts at industry research institutes;
- to eliminate bureaucratic influence on the process of certification of experts;
- to replace the scheme of re-certification every three years with a scheme of experts taking refresher courses every five years, with the expert being selected as a narrow-profile specialisation;
- to improve the structure of forensic institutions by expanding the staff of experts and reducing the number of managerial positions;
- to develop a system to increase motivation to work in forensic science³⁷.

Integrating these proposals into the practical field of forensic experts' activities will optimise the examination process, which will generally positively impact the effectiveness of the fight against crime in Ukraine, including in the context of war crimes investigation. Also, it is advisable to attract practical experience in improving the legal support of forensic examination in developed countries.

4-1: ASPECTS OF EUROPEAN EXPERIENC

According to the report "Forensic Expertise: Practices of Foreign Countries", which is the result of the European Union's Pravo-Justice Project³⁸, the national legislative framework of the vast majority of European countries (including the Baltic States) requires

³⁵ Bazhaniuk, V. V. (2023). *Id.*

³⁶ Perederii, O. (2022). *Id.*

³⁷ Monitoring report for 2021 (2022). *Ministry of Justice of Ukraine. Directorate of Justice and Criminal Justice.* <https://justtalk.com.ua/post/kriminalna-yustitsiya-u-2021-rotsi-oglyad-monitoringovogo-zvitu-minyustu>

³⁸ European Union's Pravo-Justice Project. (2022). *Pravo-Justice.* <https://www.pravojustice.eu/>

that experts have the appropriate qualifications in the field of forensic examination. Also, the expert must confirm his or her professional qualifications (typical for France, Germany, Italy, Lithuania, Latvia).

In European practice, a forensic expert must possess general basic skills for the effective conduct of any examination, as well as specialised skills in certain selected areas of forensic science. These competences are usually acquired through formal education, specialised training and practical experience. At the same time, within the national legislative framework, Article 34 of the Law of Ukraine No. 2145-VIII “On Education” dated 05.09.2017 “On Education” that the learning outcomes and competences required for the award of professional qualifications can be achieved through formal, non-formal or informal education³⁹.

Thus, Ukraine’s legislation provides for the acquisition of a forensic expert’s professional qualification not only within the framework of formal education in educational institutions but also through informal education. The latter includes independent mastery of skills and knowledge and the accumulation of practical experience in forensic science.

Today, special attention is required to use the potential of integrated competence-based approaches to confirm the qualifications of a forensic expert in Ukraine. This approach minimises the risks of erroneous forensic conclusions, reduces the risks of human error, and meets the requirements of the modern legal framework of the international format. Thus, in the aforementioned report of the European Union’s Pravo-Justice Project⁴⁰, among the general skills of a forensic expert, which are characterised by the primary need, the specialist’s awareness of the need for continuous education and professional development is highlighted. In fact, in the modern legal environment, continuing education is positioned as the determining criterion for assessing an expert’s competence, along with accreditation conditions and the use of innovative scientific and technological achievements. These requirements are stipulated by the most influential international documents in forensic science, in particular, ENFSI and CEPEJ. They are also reflected in the national legal norms of most European countries in the format of specialised laws on forensic science.

At the same time, the expert institution or the forensic expert himself is given the right to make an independent decision on advanced training and professional development. Thus, on the one hand, in the developed European community, there is a legally binding obligation to participate in continuous training regularly. On the other hand, experts’ professional development forms and mechanisms are not regulated in the legal field due to the specifics of forensic examination. A forensic institution or expert can independently choose the training to participate in or the institutions to improve their qualification level and develop their professional competences.

The upgrade of the legal support for the professional selection of forensic experts should provide for the abolition of re-certification of forensic experts and integrate the

³⁹ On education: Law of Ukraine of 05.09.2017 No. 2145-VIII, (as amended), *Verhovna Rada of Ukraine*, (2017). <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2145-19#Text>

⁴⁰ *Pravo-Justice*. (2022). *Id.*

opportunities for advanced training of experts in the manner of their choice. This may include participation in seminars and workshops and teaching or research activities in forensic science. The expert should have the right to choose the method of acquiring professional competences and advanced training, which will encourage him or her to continue professional development.

5: SCHOLARLY PERSPECTIVES ON THE RESEARCHED ISSUES

Current industry studies see the active involvement of the potential of digital technologies in the process of expert research as one of the ways to optimise the forensic system. In particular, Coulthard⁴¹ considers the possibility of digitalising a significant share of processes. Biedermann and Kotsoglou⁴² position the primary goal of this process as ensuring the reliability and objective interpretation of the information obtained.

Dror et al.⁴³ focus on the possibilities of forensic experts' continuous professional development in implementing a fair justice policy. The scientists emphasise the need for profile differentiation of the professional activities of forensic experts. At the same time, Garrett et al.⁴⁴ note that the state's implementation of fair justice functions in the digital age requires additional measures to control the safety and quality of the examination process.

The results of the study by Neuteboom et al.⁴⁵ include evidence that the purpose of the generally accepted ISO17025 standard as a standard for the forensic science continuum is not met. The researchers report a low level of expert opinion, which is explained by the lack of identification of several required competences, including cognitive ones. They are not monitored or evaluated, and the incentive for an expert to obtain accreditation and continuous improvement is internal rather than legislatively formulated. The researchers are convinced that the forensic science community needs to reconsider its approach to quality management to have continued value and relevance in the future.

Doyle⁴⁶ positions the priority of innovative development in the system of judicial system transformation against the backdrop of crisis and instability. Doyle⁴⁷ examines

⁴¹ Coulthard, M. (2020). *Id.*

⁴² Biedermann, A., & Kotsoglou, K. N. (2021). *Id.*

⁴³ Dror, I. E., Scherr, K. C., Mohammed, L. A., MacLean, C. L., & Cunningham, L. (2021). Biasability and reliability of expert forensic document examiners. *Forensic science international*, 318, 110610. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forsciint.2020.110610>

⁴⁴ Garrett, B. L., Crozier, W. E., & Grady, R. (2020). Error rates, likelihood ratios, and jury evaluation of forensic evidence. *Journal of Forensic Sciences*, 65(4), 1199-1209. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1556-4029.14323>

⁴⁵ Neuteboom, W., Ross, A., Bugeja, L., Willis, S., Roux, C., & Lothridge, K. (2024). *Id.*

⁴⁶ Doyle, S. (2020). *Id.*

the effectiveness of the Quality Standards Framework (QSF) supporting forensic science in Australia, New Zealand, Europe, and North America. At the same time, Doyle⁴⁸ introduces the concept of hierarchy in classifying standards for better orientation in the legal landscape. The researchers also identified risks to QSF and opportunities for improving the legal support of forensic experts and their professional selection.

According to Jühling et al.⁴⁹, the actualisation of the issue of ensuring the reliability of expert opinions requires the introduction of innovative management solutions and digital optimisation opportunities in the field of research. In the information security sphere, scholars see the need to implement comprehensive measures to prevent information expansion and integration into the global information space while maintaining the autonomy of the national security sphere. Digital tools should help ensure the formation of objective expert opinions; therefore, their possession should serve as a factor in the professional selection of forensic experts.

At the same time, as this study shows, against the backdrop of wartime crisis phenomena, which are expressed in numerous war crimes, there is a need not only to increase the level of professional competence of forensic experts but also to reduce the risks of the determining influence of the human factor. In this regard, the professional selection of experts should consider a set of psychophysiological requirements to improve the quality of their core functions. These measures should be integrated into the regulatory and legal support of fair justice, allowing for effective defence of its interests in the event of destabilising effects of external and internal wartime threats and increased risks of war crimes.

CONCLUSION

6:

As the study results confirm, forensic experts play an important role in ensuring the reliability of expert opinions and the objectivity of justice. The level of their qualifications and experience is a determining factor in influencing the correctness of decisions. In this regard, a forensic expert must be a competent specialist in their field and strive to constantly improve their professional level.

Practice shows significant gaps in the regulatory and legal support of the professional selection process of forensic experts. Aspects of their training, certification and practice have several shortcomings: lack of unified requirements for the competence of forensic experts, unregulated procedure for their certification, and inaccessibility of internships and advanced training. In general, the competence of a forensic expert, in addition to information on education, is also evidenced by

⁴⁷ Doyle, S. (2020). *Id.*

⁴⁸ Doyle, S. (2020). *Id.*

⁴⁹ Jühling, M., König, L. M., Gruber, H., Wolf, V., Ritz-Timme, S., & Mayer, F. (2023). *Id.*

postgraduate education and advanced training, academic rank and academic degree in the field of forensic specialisation, experience in scientific and pedagogical and training activities, experience in expert work, participation in scientific and communication events, supervision of persons intending to obtain (confirm) the qualification of a forensic expert and the number of trained forensic experts.

To eliminate the shortcomings in the Ukrainian reality, it is advisable to introduce several optimisation and preventive measures, including the maximum unification of national procedural legislation on forensic examination. It should provide favourable conditions for implementing generally accepted European standards for developing higher professional education in forensic science and advanced training of forensic experts. It is also necessary to reduce the bureaucratic impact on the certification process of experts and upgrade the traditional certification scheme in the context of the priority of narrow-profile specialisation of forensic experts. The legal framework should enshrine a new concept for the structure of forensic institutions, which provides for expanding the staff of experts and minimising the number of managerial positions. It is advisable to consider the successful experience of developed countries in terms of the increasing motivation to work in forensic examination.

Optimising changes to existing legislation should improve the training process, maintain the qualification level, and ensure the professional selection of forensic experts. The general skills required by a forensic expert include an awareness of the need for continuous education and training and digital competence. At the same time, integrating competence-based approaches to confirm a forensic expert's qualifications deserves special attention. This will contribute to further developing the expert community and improving the forensic science system in Ukraine, particularly in the context of war crimes investigations.

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